

Article

Moving Towards Paperless Administration

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ABSTRACT

In India the education administration process still is paper based. All official documents like admission, attendance, examination, fees and degrees are mainly paper based. Instead of paper the paperless administration would use modern technology to accomplish all of the same goals. Going paperless can make documentation and Information sharing easier, keep personal information more secure and help the environment too. Institutions can practice better paperless administration using various digital tools. The digitalization with Complete E governance ensures paperless administration process. This paper mainly focuses on importance of paperless Administration, challenges, solutions to go towards paperless administration, how to make effective use of technology for paperless administration, benefits of paperless administration, effective use of 3 R's Reduce, Reuse, Recycle and the effective paperless educational management system.

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1. Introduction

In day-to-day life papers is the number one material thrown away and one of the biggest populated industries. 100% paperless Administration is may not be possible but few good initiatives can definitely help in reducing the use of papers in administration. Paper is a part of our everyday life and we should use it wisely.

Paperless Administration concept was introduced in 1980s. Paperless administration is a work environment in which the use of paper is eliminated or greatly reduced. This is done by converting documents and other papers into digital form and this process is known as digitization, with the help of paperless Administration we can save money, boost productivity, save space, make documentation and Information sharing easier and keep the personal information more secure.

2. Benefits of paperless Administration

- It increases productivity.
- It increases security
- It saves money.
- It simplifies storage space.
- Effective disaster recovery protection.
- Keep environment healthy.
- Improve Institutions competitiveness.
- Automatic backup.
- Data can be easily saved and retrieved.
- Communication is faster.
- We can keep everything well organised.
- Time saving.
- Easy to access.

3. Challenges of Paperless Administration

Institution May encounter technological Challenges such as:

- File format compatibility
- Longevity of digital document
- System stability
- Employees and clients not having appropriate technological skill

- The cost of the hardware and the software
- The need of training
- Security failure
- Hardware failure.
- Lack of management initiative mandate
- We need physical signature on paper
- Staff prefer paper for handling / reading
- Lack of understanding of paper free option
- Paper provides a more reliable /auditable
- Not cost effective to provide suitable

4. Strategies for a paperless administration

A. Explore and identify the areas where your institution utilises the paper

- How much paper do you use for events, notices, letters for printing papers keep record of it?
- Which paper product is used?
- Have a survey of all departments of the institution that the paper they are using, where it is coming from, what purpose they are using it, how they are using it.
- Keep track on the expenditures on the paper product.

B. Divide the target areas for paper reduction plan: -

- Implement the paper reduction plan by following the sustainability concept of 3R'S that is Reduce, Reuse and Recycle. Reduce paper consumption and switch to paperless Administration.
- Recycle paper that has been used.
- Make a habit of reuse single sided scraped paper.

C. Education and training

- Emphasis on following the paperless administration goal.
- Define when what and how's and Why's of your plan.
- Organise training for the people of the institution.

- If you achieve little success celebrate it, it gives motivation.
- Identify areas for the improvement

D. Measure the progress

- Regularly monitor the success of your plan or program.
- Share your success stories with employees, staff, stakeholders and parent Institution.
- Take good initiative from the stakeholders in this process.

E. General best practices for the paperless administration

- Reduce offline junk mail.
- Recycle all papers and newspapers
- Use various electronic tools to share, store and Sync notes across devices including desktop, computers, laptops, tablets and phones.
- For meetings promote video conferencing use Zoom, Google meet, webex etc.
- Attendees can register and submit payment online.
- You can send agenda of the meeting and take survey online
- Newsletters for Communications.
- Think before you print your copy and ask yourself do; I really need to print this?
- Print only what is necessary
- Be selective
- Print in black and white colour.
- Set up printers' copies copiers and computer for double sided printing.
- Go Digital work on edit, save, share, send and receive documents in electronic format.
- Implement paperless meetings
- Minimise the margin of the document letter size and line spacing
- Minimise the use of efficient fonts because this Fonts use significantly less space.
- Stop distributing unnecessary handout during meetings seminars
- Go with paperless electronic form
- Print multiple slides per page

- Provide half size sheet.
- Change the paper cups used napkins paper towels and toilet paper conservatively

F. Reuse scrap paper reuse envelopes packaging.

Paperless Education Management system

- Students profiling
- Online admission
- Fees and instalments
- Parent communication
- Library management
- Live chat forum

Student profiling

- Student information
- Parent information
- Students' documents (e-filing)
- Academic information

Online admission: -

- Online admission forms
- Reservation and quotas
- Accept and reject authorisations
- SMS and email updates

Fees and instalments: -

- Configure instalment
- Automatic reminders
- Bank challans
- Parent communication
- SMS inbox email inbox

Library Management: -

- Book catalogues
- Book issues and return

Live chat forum: -

- Freedom of location
- Exchange of ideas
- Online support.

5. Conclusion

Paperless administration is about changing behaviour, it is all about people and the institutions culture, different tools only can help you to get there

the institution must have a vision goal and plan, to achieve those goals gradually and then execute it successfully to move towards a paperless administration. It is an evolution and it is not going to happen overnight it will lead constant and tireless efforts by each and every member of the institution. To reduce or eliminate paper, institution needs to set the proper guidelines and give permission to its employees to use different electronic tools. It also helps the environment the less paper we use the less trees are chopped down to make it.

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